

CO-CREATING THE GREENSCENT APPS: SEEING THE RESULTS

HOW WAS THE INITIAL FEEDBACK APPLIED,
AND WHAT TO DO NEXT?

**“SEEING THE RESULTS MADE ME
FEEL LIKE I HAVE CONTRIBUTED
TO THE START OF A GREENER
EUROPE”**

INTRODUCTION

Participation is more than just letting the voices of citizens be heard. A true participatory process demands that those voices are actually included as a core aspect of the innovation process. This idea formed the basis for the 5th round of Youth Assembly workshops, which were held on June 25th.

WORKSHOP AGENDA

Part 1) How was the feedback applied in the GreenSCENT apps?

In the first part of the workshop, Alessandro Polini from Uninettuno presented how the Youth Assemblies ideas and feedback had been applied to the GreenSCENT apps.

Part 2) How was the initial feedback applied in the Augmented Reality App, and what's next?

The second part of the workshop was spent together with Diana Urquiza from BCS. Diana presented the progress made in the Augmented Reality app, and invited the young participants for another round of feedback.

Part 3) Designing the in-person meetings together with the participants

We asked the participants to co-design some of the activities on the in-person meetings. The participants created social activities which they were asked to facilitate on the in-person meetings. Also, they were invited to provide ideas on local activities related to the green deal competences.

HOW WAS THE FEEDBACK APPLIED?

PART 1 - THE GREENSCENT APPS

During the previous workshops, the young participants in the GreenSCENT Youth Assemblies have provided the GreenSCENT project and its partners with invaluable input to the pilots and demonstrators which are under development: They have brainstormed, generated ideas, provided feedback, and discussed creative ways of integrating some-times abstract concepts into real-life scenarios.

Accordingly, we think it is important to demonstrate to the participants how their efforts have been utilized and continue to influence the outcomes of the project.

With this in mind, Alessandro Pollini from UNINETTUNO was invited to the workshop to provide an overview of the progress made in the development of three distinct apps: Environmental Monitoring, Citizen Journalism, and Interactive Documentaries. These apps were initially explored by the YA participants during the workshops held in February, and with Alessandro's presentation the participants got to see the results of their inputs.

TIME MACHINE	DATA ASSEMBLIES	ON FIELD CHALLENGES	SAVE THE KNOWLEDGE
Scenario navigation Alternative futures exploration to support critical thinking	Data manipulation and exploration See the level of relationship between entities Comparison between data Cause-effect relationship	Collaborative storytelling > format for documentary Peer learning / Contest / Story modules Bottom-up emergent learning Challenge-based / mission-based learning	Commonplace book Heritage / place based / trans generation exchanges Multimedia / shared scrapbook Individual / collective shared knowledge > serendipity / novel connections

Excerpt from Alessandro Polinis presentation:

Alessandro presented how **four design concepts** were developed based on the participants' ideas and feedback, together with other internal and external brainstorms and activities. The young participants could recognise all four concepts from their ideas and feedback.

HOW WAS THE FEEDBACK APPLIED?

PART 2 - THE AUGMENTED REALITY APP?

During the workshop, we also revisited the Augmented Reality app which the participants had previously engaged with back in February. This time, we were joined by Diana Urquiza from Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), who presented how the valuable feedback provided by the participants had been incorporated into the development of the app.

Additionally, the participants had the opportunity to offer their feedback on the interactive lessons within the app, enabling Diana and her team to refine and tailor these educational experiences to better cater to the needs of students.

Excerpt from Diana Urquiza's presentation

IT'S IMPORTANT FOR PARTICIPANTS TO SEE THE RESULTS OF THEIR COMMITMENT

Seeing and discussing the concrete change as a result of the participants involvement helped the participants gain increased confidence in both the value they deliver to the project as well as in the prospect of a greener future.

As a response to the changes made to the apps, one participant said, ***“It made us feel helpful, because our suggestions were used. We are also happy and excited to see the end result. The app could be useful if implemented right.”*** While another participant profoundly said that ***“Seeing the results made me feel like I have contributed to the start of a greener Europe”***.

We are beyond happy to see how the Youth Assemblies enable the young participants to recognize themselves as changemakers. Becoming aware of the value they bring to the table is an important step towards empowerment, and hopefully they can use it to inspire other youths. As one participant importantly said, it ***“makes me feel like it matters that we participate in these workshops”***. And it really does!

“

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**A special thanks to all participants in the
GreenSCENT Youth Assemblies for engaging in
developing ideas and sharing reflections and
insights on the green apps.**